

Systematic Verification of the 3D Random Ray Code THETA Against International Shielding Benchmarks

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ABSTRACT

Accurate three-dimensional (3D) radiation shielding analysis is essential for nuclear engineering. The Random Ray Method (TRRM), a stochastic variant of Method Of Characteristics (MOC), has emerged as a promising tool for complex 3D radiation shielding calculations. Based on TRRM, a 3D particle transport code named THETA is recently developed to solve large-scale, complex shielding problems. THETA implements several key features for practical engineering applications: an automated "map2mesh" module for discretizing global Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) models onto a Cartesian mesh, support for diverse source definitions, and a dual-level MPI/OpenMP hybrid parallel strategy. THETA is systematically verified against three representative and challenging benchmarks: ASPIS Iron-88, VENUS-3, and HBR-2. For the ASPIS deep penetration problem, THETA's results show excellent agreement with the reference TORT code and good agreement with experimental data for threshold reaction rates. In the highly heterogeneous VENUS-3 benchmark, THETA demonstrates strong predictive accuracy, with approximately 95% of the 386 detector measurements falling within a $\pm 10\%$ deviation from experimental values. Finally, in the simulation of the HBR-2 benchmark derived from commercial reactor, THETA yields an average Calculated-to-Experimental (C/E) ratio of 1.033 at the surveillance capsule and 1.103 in the reactor cavity (excluding known measurement errors), demonstrating good agreement. These results validate THETA as an accurate and robust tool for complex 3D shielding analysis.

Keywords: Radiation shielding, the random ray method, ASPIS Iron-88, VENUS-3, HBR-2

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate and efficient radiation shielding analysis is a cornerstone of nuclear engineering, essential for ensuring nuclear safety, calculating biological dose rates, and assessing the integrity of reactor components such as the pressure vessel. The demand for high-fidelity simulation tools has grown significantly with the development of advanced reactor concepts, including small modular reactors (SMRs) and microreactors, which often feature complex geometries and compact shielding configurations. These new designs necessitate robust three-dimensional (3D) transport codes that can precisely model complex geometries and accurately predict particle flux attenuation through thick shielding.

The Method of Characteristics (MOC) [1], as a powerful deterministic approach, has seen extensive application in reactor core physics calculations. However, its extension to three-dimensional (3D) calculations is hindered by significant computational challenges. Traditional 3D MOC requires extremely dense characteristic ray segments, requiring unacceptable computational time and substantial computational memory. While specialized 3D MOC implementations have been shown to efficiently handle certain classes of PWR analysis [2], deterministic 3D MOC becomes highly inefficient for general-purpose 3D transport. Besides, 3D MOC suffers from a significant memory drawback as it must store all angular flux values at the domain boundaries between iterations. Furthermore, its

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reliance on fixed angular quadrature sets makes it susceptible to the ray effect [3]. Consequently, these limitations have restricted its viability for large-scale 3D radiation transport simulations. To address these challenges, the Random Ray Method (TRRM)[4], a stochastic variant of MOC proposed by Tramm, has emerged as a promising alternative. TRRM replaces the deterministic angular quadrature of MOC with stochastically sampled rays. This stochastic approach inherently eliminates the ray effect. More importantly, for 3D calculations, TRRM demonstrates a significant advantage by achieving comparable accuracy with lower density of characteristic rays. Besides, the on-the-fly tracking of TRRM significantly loose the requirement of memory footprint. These attributes make TRRM a promising tool for complex 3D radiation shielding analyses, which has been preliminarily demonstrated by Tramm and Cosgrove [5].

Motivated by these findings, a 3D particle transport code named THETA (Tracking-based Hybrid monte carlo-moc Efficient Tracking Application) [6] is recently developed. THETA is specifically designed to solve large-scale, complex 3D shielding problems. It implements an efficient 3D ray tracing on structured Cartesian grid and is designed with a domain decomposition parallelization strategy to leverage modern high-performance computing (HPC) architectures, enabling the high-resolution simulation of full-scale reactor problems. Based on THETA, we have already demonstrated TRRM's superiority over the Monte Carlo method in deep penetration problems, validated through rigorous comparisons under multigroup and high-order scattering conditions [7]. Additionally, its feasibility in the calculation of fast neutron fluence rates in reactor pressure vessels has been assessed [8].

However, these previous studies did not involve verification against complex, large-scale realistic engineering benchmarks, which is essential for demonstrating the practical capabilities of the THETA code. In this study, three internationally recognized benchmarks including ASPIS Iron-88 [9], VENUS-3 [10], and HBR-2 [11] are selected, and the computational results from THETA are compared against experimental measurements and results from other established transport codes.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of TRRM method and THETA code. Section 3 presents and discusses the numerical results of THETA. Section 4 provides conclusions and discussion.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. The Random Ray Method

While the Random Ray Method (TRRM) and the Method of Characteristics (MOC) are both derived from the same fundamental transport theory, their distinction lies in the generation of characteristic rays. TRRM utilizes N "disordered" characteristic rays produced through uniform random sampling other than the parallel rays employed in MOC, which are deterministically generated based on a fixed angular quadrature set and predefined ray spacing. During a single TRRM transport sweep, N random rays are first generated, and for l -th ray in these rays: 1) A random starting position r_l is sampled uniformly from within the 3D problem domain. 2) A random direction $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_l$ is sampled from an isotropic angular distribution.

Once a ray ($r_l, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_l$) is generated, it is traced through the 3D Flat-Source Region (FSR) meshes under a pre-defined termination length. During this process, the trajectory of this ray is partitioned into multiple segments by the boundaries of the discrete FSRs. For the k -th segment of this ray, the transport equation can be simplified as:

$$\frac{d\psi_{g,i,l,k}(s)}{ds} + \Sigma_{t,g,i}\psi_{g,i,l,k}(s) = Q_{g,i} \quad (1)$$

where g is the index of energy group, i is the index of FSR, s is the distance along this segment, $\psi_{g,i,l,k}(s)$ is the flux of this ray, $\Sigma_{t,g,i}$ and $Q_{g,i}$ are the group-wised total cross-section and source strength in the i -th FSR, respectively.

The angular flux of this ray is updated by the analytical solution of Equation (1):

$$\psi_{g,i,l,k}(s) = \psi_{g,i,l,k}(0) \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s} + \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} \left(1 - \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s}\right) \quad (2)$$

where $\psi_{g,i,l,k}(0)$ is the incoming flux of ray on this segment.

The contribution of this segment for the scalar flux in the i -th FSR is calculated by:

$$\Delta\psi_{g,i,l,k} = \left[\psi_{g,i,l,k}(0) - \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} \right] \left(1 - \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s_{l,k}}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\psi_{g,i,l,k}$ is the contribution, $s_{l,k}$ is the length of this segment.

The scalar flux in i -th FSR after a transport sweep is calculated by:

$$\phi_{g,i} = \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} + \frac{\sum_{l=1}^{L_i} \sum_{k=1}^{K_l} \Delta\psi_{g,i,l,k}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i} \sum_{l=1}^{L_i} \sum_{k=1}^{K_l} s_{l,k}} \quad (4)$$

where $\phi_{g,i}$ is the group-wised scalar flux in i -th FSR, L_i is number of rays intersecting with i -th FSR, K_l is the number of times the l -th ray intersecting with the i -th FSR.

It should be considered that Equations (2) and (3) are dependent on the ray's initial angular flux. Owing to the stochastic generation of rays in TRRM, it is necessary to assume an isotropic angular flux at the starting position of each ray. Consequently, the ray cannot validly contribute to the scalar flux tally at the beginning of its track. To eliminate the errors introduced by the initial flux guess, a user-defined "dead zone" is employed. Within this distance, the angular flux is updated via Equation (2) to allow it to reach the state consistent with local sources and cross-sections before any scalar flux accumulation is performed.

The procedure described above outlines a single TRRM transport sweep. Analogous to MOC, TRRM requires iterative transport sweeps to achieve source convergence. However, owing to the inherent stochasticity of TRRM, the calculation does not terminate once the source has converged. Following source convergence, the transport sweep process must be continually repeated, and the results from each sweep are accumulated. This two-stage procedure is analogous to the inactive and active batches utilized in Monte Carlo simulations.

2.2. Features of THETA

THETA (Tracking-based Hybrid monte carlo-moc Efficient Tracking Application) is a recently-developed 3D particle transport code designed to make TRRM practical for complex, engineering-grade shielding analysis. The key features are detailed as follows:

Geometry and meshing: An automated geometry workflow is adopted in THETA. A "map2mesh" module automatically discretizes a single, global Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) geometry model onto a Cartesian grid, which serves as the FSR meshes. This module uses a voxelization algorithm to determine material for each cell. This automated mapping is similar to the TRRM implementation in SCONE [12] and OpenMC [13]. It eliminates the need for users to manually define a unique CSG representation for every single FSR, making complex TRRM modeling feasible.

Cross-section and source definition: THETA offers flexibility in data input, directly reading microscopic cross-sections in the legacy binary ANISN format or accepting pre-calculated macroscopic cross-sections from the user. It supports various source configurations, including point, mesh-based, and material-based sources. A point source is now treated as a uniform volumetric source within the containing FSR.

Higher-order Scattering Source and Linear Source Approximation: To enhance physical fidelity and computational efficiency, THETA implements the higher-order anisotropic scattering source and includes an optional Linear Source Region (LSR) approximation, which can achieve comparable accuracy to the standard FSR method but on significantly coarser meshes. The theory for these treatments follows Reference 11.

User-friendly IO & Visualization: All input files utilize the structured, human-readable XML format, parsed via the open-source pugixml library. For model verification, THETA can generate 2D slice plots of the geometry directly from the input file. Furthermore, the code outputs the FSR-wise particle flux spectrum in both a simple text format and the RectilinearGrid VTK format. The latter enables integration with powerful, open-source scientific visualization tools such as ParaView and VisIt, facilitating in-depth post-processing and analysis.

High-Performance Parallel Computing: To address the extreme computational demands of 3D shielding, THETA is engineered with a dual-level hybrid parallel strategy. It uses MPI for inter-node domain decomposition on distributed-memory clusters and OpenMP for intra-node, thread-safe ray-level parallelism, maximizing efficiency on modern HPC architectures. For inter-node domain decomposition, the global geometry is partitioned into several sub-domains assigned to different MPI ranks. When a random ray reaches a domain boundary, its current state (position, direction, and angular flux) is packaged and sent to the neighboring processor using non-blocking MPI calls. This ensures the continuity of the ray trajectory across the entire problem space.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. ASPIS Iron-88 Benchmark

ASPIS Iron-88 benchmark [9] includes detector measurements at multiple, progressively deeper locations within the thick iron shielding, which provides valuable data to verify the accuracy of THETA in modeling neutron attenuation through substantial shielding thickness. This benchmark features a NESTOR-driven fission plate source and an 88-cm shield composed of 14 steel plates. Gaps between steel plates are inserted with activation foils attached to thin aluminum carriers to measure different reaction rates. The measured reaction rates include the Au-197(n, γ), Rh-103(n, n'), In-115(n, n'), S-32(n, p), and Al-27(n, α) reactions. To map the spatial neutron distribution, same dosimeters are placed at various gap locations within the shielding assembly.

The THETA calculation is performed using a conservative set of parameters. The computational domain is discretized with an approximately 1cm \times 1cm \times 1cm mesh, resulting in a total of 201 \times 250 \times 204 FSR meshes. For the transport calculation, 300,000 characteristic rays are utilized. A dead zone length of 350 cm and a maximum tracking length of 1000 cm are specified for each ray. The simulation involved 1000 total batches, with the first 100 serving as inactive batches for source convergence. A P_3 scattering source order is applied to consider scattering anisotropy. The cross-sections used in this study are from BUGLE-96 library [15].

Figure 1 compares the C/E distribution of Rh-103(n, n') and S-32(n, p) reaction rates obtained from experimental measurements, the TORT calculation [9], and the THETA calculation. As can be seen, the THETA results are in excellent agreement with the TORT results (reference), with the two profiles being nearly identical. Table I presents the average C/E (Calculated-to-Experimental) ratios for all positions and all dosimeters. It is evident that for the four threshold reactions, the THETA and TORT results are highly consistent. However, a larger discrepancy is observed between the two codes for the Au-197(n, γ) dosimeter. Since this reaction is more sensitive in the thermal energy range, this suggests a deviation in the thermal neutron spectra between THETA and TORT. This issue should be re-investigated after increasing the number of inactive batches in the THETA calculation. Furthermore, the multi-group cross-section and spatial discretization may also contribute to this discrepancy. Although the BUGLE-96 library has been widely validated, discrepancy may be reduced by updating the shielding cross-sections with more recent evaluated nuclear data libraries. Besides, given that the mean free path of neutrons is shorter in thermal energy ranges, a more refined mesh may be required to achieve higher accuracy.

3.2. VENUS-3 Benchmark

The VENUS-3 benchmark [10] utilizes a zero-power experimental reactor configuration designed to simulate the internal structural features of a PWR pressure vessel. Its primary value for code verification is from the comprehensive and spatially diverse detector layout, which facilitates a far more rigorous assessment of transport codes than benchmarks restricted to sparse or localized measurements. A defining characteristic of the facility is its significant three-dimensional heterogeneity introduced by Partial Length Shielded Assemblies (PLSAs). The core's horizontal layout includes a central water hole and an inner stainless steel baffle. The fuel region surrounds this baffle, composed of an inner 4.0% enriched UO_2 zone and an outer 3.3% enriched UO_2 zone, the latter of which partially contains the PLSAs. This region is enclosed by successive layers: an outer stainless steel baffle, a water reflector, the core barrel, a water gap, and a 6.72 cm thick neutron pad. Detailed material and geometric specifications are documented in Reference 8. To map the 3D neutron flux distribution, 386 detectors are positioned at various axial and radial locations. These detectors relied on three threshold reactions: Ni-58(n, p), In-115(n, n'), and Al-27(n, α).

Figure 1. Comparison of C/E distributions of Rh-103(n, n') and S-32(n, p) reaction rates for ASPIS Iron-88 benchmark

Table I. Averaged C/E ratio for different dosimeters of ASPIS Iron-88 benchmark.

Dosimeter	Averaged C/E of TORT	Averaged C/E of THETA
Au-197(n, γ)	1.048	0.933
Rh-103(n, n')	1.034	1.019
In-115(n, n')	0.878	0.871
S-32(n, p)	0.817	0.832
Al-27(n, α)	1.257	1.269

The THETA calculation is performed using the same FSR division as Reference 8. For the transport calculation, 600,000 characteristic rays are utilized. A dead zone length of 300 cm and a maximum tracking length of 3000 cm are specified for each ray. The simulation involved 1100 total batches, with the first 1000 serving as inactive batches for source convergence. A P_3 scattering source order is applied to consider scattering anisotropy. The cross-sections used are from BUGLE-96 library.

The equivalent fission fluxes converted from reaction rates results of THETA calculation are compared with the experiment values. As shown in Figure 2 to Figure 4, the THETA calculations demonstrate strong agreement with the experimental data. An analysis of the C/E ratios for the 386 detectors reveals that a significant majority, 270 detectors (~70%), show results within the $\pm 5\%$ experimental uncertainty range (C/E between 0.95 and 1.05). Besides, 367 detectors (~95%) falling within a $\pm 10\%$ deviation (0.9 to 1.1). The C/E ratios for the entire set of detectors are bounded between 0.8 and 1.2, which is well within the acceptable criteria for shielding analysis.

Figure 2. Comparison of equivalent fission flux for Al dosimeter of VENUS-3 benchmark

Figure 3. Comparison of equivalent fission flux for In dosimeter of VENUS-3 benchmark

Figure 4. Comparison of equivalent fission flux for Ni dosimeter of VENUS-3 benchmark

3.3. HBR-2 Benchmark

The HBR-2 benchmark [11] is a well-established and internationally recognized problem, which is based on experimental measurements performed at the H.B. Robinson Unit 2, a commercial Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR). This configuration effectively challenges the capability of 3D transport codes to accurately model the complicated reactor shielding. The detailed description of this benchmark is in Reference 9.

For the THETA calculation, the geometry model explicitly represents all key components of the benchmark. This includes the core baffle, core barrel, thermal shield, the multi-layered RPV, and the cavity regions including thermal insulation and the detector well structure. Fuel assemblies are modeled as homogenized regions as defined in the benchmark specifications. For the spatial discretization, the radial plane is defined with a 2x2 FSRs for each intra-core fuel pin. The surrounding ex-core region is meshed using a 1 cm x 1 cm FSR near to the core and a 2 cm x 2 cm FSR in more distant areas. A uniform axial mesh height of 2 cm is used throughout the model. For the transport calculation,

1,500,000 characteristic rays are utilized. A dead zone length of 350 cm and a maximum tracking length of 2500 cm are specified for each ray. The simulation involved 1100 total batches, with the first 1000 serving as inactive batches for source convergence. A P_3 scattering source order is applied to consider scattering anisotropy. The cross-sections used are from BUGLE-96 library. The source spatial distribution is based on the cycle-average, pin-by-pin power distributions provided in the benchmark data files.

The C/E ratio of different dosimeters at surveillance capsule and reactor cavity are provided in Table II. As shown, the results from THETA demonstrate good agreement with the measurements at the surveillance capsule location. The maximum C/E deviation is 1.100, with an average C/E of 1.033 for the six dosimeters. In the reactor cavity, the discrepancies increase. Notably, the calculated Np-237(n, f) reaction rate is significantly lower than the experimental value, a discrepancy primarily attributed to an error in the measurement value [11]. For the other dosimeters in the cavity, all C/E values are within the shielding calculation limit of 20%, and the average C/E is 1.103.

Table II. C/E ratio for different dosimeters of HBR-2 benchmark.

	Np-237(n, f)	U-238(n, f)	Ni-58(n, p)	Fe-54(n, p)	Ti-46(n, p)	Cu-63(n, α)
Surveillance capsule	0.976	0.957	1.100	1.090	1.015	1.063
Reactor cavity	0.729	0.913	1.174	1.185	1.112	1.133

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a recently developed three-dimensional particle transport code, THETA based on the Random Ray Method (TRRM) is systematically verified against three representative and challenging radiation shielding benchmarks. The code implements several key features designed for practical engineering applications, including an automated "map2mesh" workflow for CSG geometries, flexible cross-section and source definitions, higher-order anisotropic scattering, and a dual-level MPI/OpenMP hybrid parallel strategy for high-performance computing. For the ASPIS Iron-88 problem, THETA's results show excellent agreement with the reference TORT code and good agreement with experimental data for threshold reaction rates. In the highly heterogeneous VENUS-3 benchmark, THETA demonstrates strong predictive accuracy, with approximately 95% of the 386 detector measurements falling within a $\pm 10\%$ deviation from experimental values. Finally, in the simulation of the HBR-2 benchmark based on a commercial reactor, THETA-calculated results are in good agreement with measurements at the surveillance capsule (average C/E of 1.033) and acceptable C/E ratios in the reactor cavity (average of 1.103, excluding known measurement errors). The successful application to deep penetration, heterogeneous, and full-scale reactor problems validate that THETA is an accurate and robust tool for 3D shielding analysis. The drawback of this study is the use of a conservative set of parameters results in large computing cost, which is tabulated in Table III. A more systematic sensitivity analysis of these parameters will be conducted in the future.

Table III. Computing cost of THETA.

Benchmark	Hardware	Configuration	Runtime (h)
ASPIS Iron-88	AMD EPYC 9754	512 OpenMP	5.4
VENUS-3	Hygon C86 7285	640 MPI	8.0
HBR-2	Hygon C86 7285	512 MPI	49.3

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